

D2.1 – Roadmap for implementation of new services

Lead Partner:	UU
Version:	v00
Author(s) (Name, Organisation):	Jan Michalek (UiB), Otto Lange (UU), Dario Buttitta (INGV), Antonio Caracausi (INGV), Lauro Chiaraluce (INGV), Ivano Matiddi (INGV), Ronald Pijnenburg (UU), Liliana Vargas Meleza (ETHZ), Stanka Šebela (ZRC SAZU), Magdalena Aljančič (ZRC SAZU), Uroš Novak (ZRC SAZU), Oliver Heidbach (GFZ), Robert Supper (GeoSphere), Jari Joutsenvaara (UO), Marko Holma (UO), Maxim Smirnov (LTU), Christian Haberland (GFZ), Anne Lemoine (BRGM), Agathe Roullé (BRGM), Rui Fernandes
Status:	Submitted
Dissemination Level:	PU

Deliverable Abstract

This deliverable is describing a roadmap for the integration in EPOS of ten groups of Data, Data Products, Services and Software (DDSS) within the Task 2.1 of the project. The roadmap comes with a brief description of the data or tools provided and a timeline from implementation and testing up to full integration. In this roadmap document the methodology underlying the integration process is set out as well.

COPYRIGHT NOTICE

This work by Parties of the EPOS ON Project is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). The EPOS ON project is funded by the European Union Horizon Europe programme under grant n° 101131592.

QUALITY CONTROL

Date	Name	Organisation
Reviewers:	Optimisation and Evolution Board members	-

Table of Contents

1	<i>Executive summary</i>	4
2	<i>Introduction</i>	5
3	<i>Methodology</i>	6
3.1	EPOS development cycles	8
3.2	Data formats supported in EPOS Platform	10
4	<i>Plan for integration of services</i>	12
4.1	Subtask 2.1.1: Multidisciplinary data from Slovenian Karst (ZRC SAZU, INCDFP-RA, INGV)	12
4.1.1	List of services for this subtask to be integrated	12
4.2	Subtask 2.1.2: Innovative geochemical data (INGV)	13
4.2.1	List of services for this subtask to be integrated	13
4.3	Subtask 2.1.3: Data from Geo-Energy Test Beds (UU, ETH Zürich)	15
4.3.1	List of services for this subtask to be integrated	15
4.4	Subtask 2.1.4: Enhance magnetotelluric data and models (LTU)	16
4.4.1	List of services for this subtask to be integrated	16
4.5	Subtask 2.1.5: Muography density imaging (UOULU, AGH/AGH-UST)	17
4.5.1	List of services for this subtask to be integrated	18
4.6	Subtask 2.1.6: World Stress Map (GFZ)	20
4.6.1	List of services for this subtask to be integrated	20
4.7	Subtask 2.1.7: Coordinated inventory of mobile instrument pools (GFZ)	23
4.7.1	List of for this subtask to be integrated	23
4.8	Subtask 2.1.8: Harmonized data and associated data services for V_{s30}, slope, and geology (BRGM) 24	
4.8.1	List of services for this subtask to be integrated	24
4.9	Subtask 2.1.9: Computation of Rapid solutions in GNSS (UGA, UBI)	27
4.9.1	List of services for this subtask to be integrated	28
4.10	Subtask 2.1.10: Airborne survey data (GEOSPHERE)	29
4.10.1	List of services for this subtask to be integrated.....	29
4.11	Service integration timeline	31
5	<i>References</i>	33

1 Executive summary

This deliverable describes a roadmap for the implementation of new services as defined in Task 2.1 of the EPOS ON project. The document is divided into two sections. The first section describes the methodology for service integration, which has been developed in past years in EPOS. The second section of the document focuses on services defined by individual sub-tasks, collecting their description, current status, and expected timeline for integration. The timeline is rather an estimate and is subject to changes since not all integration steps are known by all the project participants by now.

2 Introduction

The EPOS (European Plate Observing System) infrastructure is a complex system that integrates data and services from various domains within solid Earth science. Currently (February 2025), there are almost 300 services integrated into the EPOS Platform. One of the objectives of the EPOS ON project is to enlarge the portfolio of available services and make them available to users in an interoperable view. There are ten subtasks defined by scientific communities in the project, focusing on various datasets and/or services to be integrated into EPOS. Those are of different maturity, and the goal of Task 2.1 is to plan and manage their successful integration.

3 Methodology

Implementation of services in the EPOS delivery framework means integration of new or already existing services into the EPOS Platform¹ (EPOS Data Portal) in a way that users can discover, visualize, and download the data. By data, we here mean observation (raw) data, processed data, or information about different sorts of objects, e.g., facilities or instruments. Data might be of a different nature (data values, images, object description, etc.). Providing access to these data through integration into EPOS (see Fig. 1) is done by means of web services (APIs). The EPOS infrastructure is a federated system, i.e., the data remains at the Service Provider server, but their descriptions are exposed through a public endpoint. The integration process is a sequence of actions that puts the web services in place with meaningful descriptions that should maximize the findability with respect to data provision. Integrating a new service into this infrastructure involves a multi-faceted approach, ensuring interoperability, standardization, and accessibility. The “interoperability” layer (Fig. 1) covers technical integration, testing and validation (see below).

Figure 1. EPOS Architecture.

Here's a breakdown of the procedure²:

1. Preparation and Planning:

¹ <https://www.epos-eu.org/dataportal>

² Backbone of the procedure steps were created with the help of [Gemini AI](#).

- **Community Engagement:** The first step involves engaging with the relevant scientific community and understanding their needs and requirements for the new service. This ensures that the service aligns with the broader goals of EPOS and addresses a genuine need within the community.
- **Technical Assessment:** A thorough technical assessment is conducted to evaluate the service's compatibility with the existing EPOS infrastructure. This includes examining data formats, communication protocols, and software dependencies.
- **Governance and Legal Considerations:** The integration process also involves addressing governance and legal aspects, such as data ownership, access rights, and licensing agreements. This ensures compliance with relevant regulations and policies.

2. Technical Integration:

- **Data and Metadata Harmonization:** If the service involves data, it needs to be harmonized with the existing EPOS metadata model³. This includes standardizing data formats, metadata descriptions, and quality control procedures.
- **API Development:** The new service needs to be exposed through well-defined APIs (Application Programming Interfaces) that allow other components of the EPOS infrastructure to interact with it. These APIs should adhere to established standards and protocols.
- **Integration with Core Services:** The service needs to be integrated with the EPOS Integrated Core Services (ICS), which provide the central hub for data and service discovery, access, and processing. This involves registering the service in the EPOS metadata catalog and ensuring seamless communication with other ICS components.

3. Testing and Validation:

- **Functional Testing:** Rigorous testing is conducted to ensure that the service functions as expected and meets the requirements of the user community.
- **Interoperability Testing:** The service is tested in conjunction with other EPOS components to verify its interoperability and seamless integration within the overall infrastructure.
- **Performance Testing:** Performance testing is carried out to assess the service's scalability and responsiveness, ensuring that it can handle the demands of the EPOS user base.

4. Deployment and Maintenance:

- **Deployment:** Once the service has passed all testing phases, it is deployed into the production environment, making it accessible to the EPOS user community.

³ <https://epos-eu.github.io/EPOS-DCAT-AP/v3/>

- **Monitoring and Maintenance:** Ongoing monitoring and maintenance are essential to ensure the service's reliability and performance. This includes addressing bug fixes, security updates, and performance optimization.

5. Documentation and Training:

- **Documentation:** Comprehensive documentation is provided to guide users on how to access and utilize the new service effectively. Service documentation is linked through metadata.
- **Training:** Training sessions and workshops may be organized to familiarize users with the service's functionalities and capabilities.

The integration of a new service into the EPOS infrastructure is a collaborative effort involving various stakeholders, including scientists, engineers, and data managers. It requires careful planning, technical expertise, and adherence to established standards and procedures. The ultimate goal is to enhance the EPOS infrastructure and provide users with seamless access to a wide range of data and services for solid Earth science research.

3.1 EPOS development cycles

EPOS implementations are scheduled into quarterly development cycles (Fig. 2), which are aligned with ICS-TCS Interaction workshops arranged in March (Q1), June (Q2), September (Q3), and December (Q4). It is expected that the integration of the new services in Task 2.1 will be aligned with these development cycles for maximum efficiency.

Development work cycles – 3 months

Figure 2. Timeline of one EPOS development cycle.

EPOS adopted the Shape Up⁴ approach (Fig.3) for planning and executing the work in individual cycles. The Shape Up Method describes the specific processes used by development teams to shape, bet, and build meaningful products. It also assesses the risks and unknowns of product development with the ultimate goal of shipping a great product on time. The work is split into individual pieces of work - pitches. Each pitch has a predefined structure and has a central document at a dedicated GitLab project repository where both planning and reporting are collected. Drafting of the pitches in the EPOS framework takes place during the ICS-TCS Interaction Workshop, which takes about one week (Fig.4). Critical days are 1) the first day where reporting from the previous cycle is taking place and 2) the last day where new pitches are presented by pitch leaders to IT Board (internal EPOS body) for assessment of feasibility, human resources and aligning with EPOS priorities. The remaining days in between are for shaping up the pitch scope during individual pitch meetings (only interested persons participating).

Figure 3. Structure of the Shape Up process

⁴<https://basecamp.com/shapeup>

Activities during ICS-TCS Interaction Workshop

Figure 4. Structure of the EPOS ICS-TCS Interaction Workshop.

All incoming requests, bugs, and observations are followed through a public issue tracker⁵ where individual issues are being assessed and tackled based on urgency and priority.

3.2 Data formats supported in EPOS Platform

EPOS Platform supports several formats which are used for various visualizations. Some formats are supported natively, and some require conversion, which is done by the central ICS server (see Table 1). Formats that do not have any supported visualization are available for download.

Table 1. Overview of currently supported formats for visualization in EPOS Platform.

Data format/payload	Native support/converted	Map visualization	Table visualization	Graph visualization
geoJSON	native	yes	yes	x
covJSON	native	x	x	yes
WMS	native	yes	x	x
WFS	native	yes	yes	x

⁵ <https://epos-ci.brgm.fr/epos-public/issuetracker/-/issues>

Data format/payload	Native support/converted	Map visualization	Table visualization	Graph visualization
geoTIFF, georeferenced PNG	converted	yes	metadata	x
QuakeML/XML (FDSN EVENT)	converted to geoJSON	yes	yes	x
stationXML	converted to geoJSON	yes	yes	x
JSON (various flavors)	converted to covJSON	x	x	yes
JSON (various flavors)	converted to geoJSON	yes	yes	x
JSON (various flavors)	converted to geoJSON	without geolocation	yes	x

4 Plan for integration of services

This chapter provides details about ten individual subtasks in Task 2.1. Some subtasks correspond to one service (e.g., integrating multiple datasets into one service), and some consist of multiple services. Some will be streamlined through well-established community services or platforms and then to EPOS, but some will require careful planning and design discussion since those are new not only to EPOS but also on their own (e.g., muography).

Each service has one Service Provider but can have multiple Data Providers. Information about both entities is collected through the EPOS metadata and exposed through the EPOS Platform, allowing proper attribution and data search.

There are two milestones in this project capturing the integration status:

- MS5 TCS services tested before integration to ICS (due M26; 31 Oct 2026)
- MS6 TCS services implemented and its sustainability plan (due M33; 31 May 2027)

The expected timeline for the integration of services is collected in [Table 2](#). The timeline is subject to changes, but most of the integration should be completed by 2027-Q2 (MS6). Integration progress will be tracked through a dedicated shared online spreadsheet called Implementation Level Matrix (ILM) which will contain criteria for assessing the integration status at any given time. The structure of ILM will resemble the integration procedure described in the previous chapter.

4.1 Subtask 2.1.1: Multidisciplinary data from Slovenian Karst (ZRC SAZU, INCDFP-RA, INGV)

Subtask description: Integration of multidisciplinary data through EIDA services from INCDFP-RA (seismic data) and FRIDGE (micro-climatic data, such as air temperature, atmospheric pressure, and CO₂) is taking place within SLO KARST NFO site (<https://slo-karst-nfo.si/>), which is situated in SW Slovenia. The area belongs to NW Dinarides, a region still undergoing active tectonic deformations (<5mm/yr) and consists mainly of highly karstified Mesozoic carbonate rocks and minor patches of Cenozoic siliciclastic flysch sequences. The main seismogenic sources of the NFO are sub-vertical dipping dextral strike-slip faults of the Dinaric fault system (NW SE and NNW SSE) with moderate to strong (historical) seismicity with occasional swarming events.

4.1.1 List of services for this subtask to be integrated

With the first steps, seismic data from 7 seismic stations: POST, MASE, PVZP, GSNE, JLSP, PLCP, and TTPJ (<https://slo-karst-nfo.si/>) will be integrated through EIDA services from NIEP (Romania). Seismic archive data for stations MPJP and ILBA that are not in operation anymore will also be integrated. Seismic stations have been in operation since 2020.

The second step will represent an integration of micro-climatic data such as air temperature, atmospheric pressure, and CO₂ from 3 monitoring sites in Postojna Cave to the FRIDGE platform and, from there, streamlined to EPOS. Micro-climatic monitoring has been taking place at hourly intervals since 2015.

List of services:

- **Seismic data from SLO KARST NFO** (<https://slo-karst-nfo.si/>)

Description: Six sites of the network are equipped with Etna2 accelerometers, and one site with a Nanometrics Titan accelerometer with Centaur datalogger. Network metadata is available here: <https://www.fdsn.org/networks/detail/S5/>. Instruments are installed in public buildings, private homes and in a cave, always on the ground floor or in the basement. Seismic data is collected in real-time and shared with EIDA Node NIEP.

Service Provider: NIEP, Romania (through EIDA).

Data Providers: Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts & Slovenian Environment Agency. (2020). *Slovenian Karst NFO Network* [Dataset]. ZRC SAZU and Slovenian Environmental Agency. <https://doi.org/10.7914/7w0j-ge89>.

- **Micro-climatic data from SLO KARST NFO** (<https://slo-karst-nfo.si/>) **situated in Postojna Cave**

Description: Two monitoring sites of the network are equipped with data loggers for hourly air temperature and air pressure measurements, and one monitoring site is equipped with a Vaisala instrument for hourly CO₂ concentrations. Monitoring has been going on since 2015.

Service Provider: ZRC SAZU to FRIDGE.

Data Providers: ZRC SAZU, Slovenia.

4.2 Subtask 2.1.2: Innovative geochemical data (INGV)

Subtask description: Access to data from natural gaseous emissions around near-fault observatories monitored by a geochemical spectrometer will be made available as a service. The novelty machine allows the retrieval of the chemical composition of the main and trace components in natural gaseous emissions and the isotopes of these gases. The monitoring can prove constraints on the deep processes controlling the mixing of fluids of different origins such as crustal vs mantle.

4.2.1 List of services for this subtask to be integrated

The integration of innovative geochemical data into the EPOS system will provide access to innovative gas emission data from Near Fault Observatories. The services provided will include data acquisition, validation, and processing to identify anomalous patterns. Once the data quality control is completed, these new time series will be available for processing, contributing to the alert system

and visualization. The chemical and isotopic data will be acquired from a selected site within the [TABOO NFO](https://taboo.ingv.it/) (Umbertide; <https://taboo.ingv.it/>).

List of services:

- **Real-time and Discrete Geochemical Data Repository**

Description: This service will provide access to a structured database containing discrete measurements of gas emissions acquired in real time from natural sources near fault zones. The data will include: concentrations of selected gaseous species, and isotopic compositions of selected components.

Service Provider: INGV.

Data Providers: INGV Sede di Palermo.

- **Machine learning-driven Data Validation and Predictive Maintenance System**

Description: This service will leverage machine learning algorithms to:

- a. Validate incoming geochemical data by detecting anomalies, sensor drift, or potential measurement errors.
- b. Predict equipment maintenance needs by analyzing performance trends of key components such as gas analyzers and power sources (e.g., batteries).
- c. Optimize maintenance schedules by identifying early signs of component degradation and recommending targeted interventions to minimize downtime.

The system will continuously learn from historical data, improving its accuracy in predicting maintenance events and detecting inconsistencies in sensor readings.

Service Provider: INGV.

Data Providers: INGV Sede di Palermo.

- **Automatic Alert System for Geochemical Anomalies**

Description: This service will implement **automated alert criteria** for detecting anomalous geochemical patterns based on predefined or dynamically adjusted thresholds. The system will:

- a. Define critical parameters (e.g., rapid increases in CO₂ flux).
- b. Use machine learning models trained on historical data to recognize early warning signs of potential geodynamic activity.

- c. Trigger real-time alerts when specific thresholds or anomalous trends are detected.

Service Provider: INGV.

Data Providers: INGV Sede di Palermo.

4.3 Subtask 2.1.3: Data from Geo-Energy Test Beds (UU, ETH Zürich)

Subtask description: Central discoverability of multidisciplinary data obtained at unique, field-scale geo-energy test bed (GETB) facilities. GETB is a subdomain in EPOS Multi-Scale Laboratories (MSL), and facilities include, among others, the Delft Campus Geothermal Project, the Fraunhofer geo-energy facilities, and the Bedretto Underground Laboratory. The data includes seismological, fiber optic sensing, electromagnetic, hydrodynamic, geological, pore fluid chemistry, core images, and petrophysical measurements on the core, enabling multidisciplinary research.

4.3.1 List of services for this subtask to be integrated

GETB data are, in most cases, stored at local repositories and are not yet made discoverable in EPOS. In this Subtask, we ensure that data are made discoverable in EPOS, 1) as GETB site-specific data collections, and 2) through multi-domain domain/TCS data dissemination, where suitable.

List of services:

- **A new MSL service for site-specific GETB data**

Description: GETB facilities are unique infrastructures collecting high-density and large-volume multi-disciplinary data pertaining to specific sites of interest to geo-energy applications or natural or induced geo-hazards. As such, a minimum requirement is to offer these data as these are collected: as site-specific data collections, made discoverable under EPOS Multi-Scale Laboratories, on the EPOS Platform. These data collections consist of medium-sized (GB) static datasets published at institutional and discipline-specific data repositories.

Service provider: Utrecht University.

Data providers: among others, 4TU.ResearchData, GFZ data services, BGS NGDC, Fraunhofer Institute, and ETH Research Collection data repository.

- **Services for multi-domain GETB data dissemination**

Description: Several of these data types are multi-domain, i.e., in addition to being offered through the site-specific GETB data service of MSL, they could simultaneously be offered by other Thematic Core Services, including potentially: Seismology (e.g., waveform data), Geological Information and Modelling (GIM, e.g., borehole data) and Multi-Scale

Laboratories (e.g. core images and petrophysics). The community effort required to make this for all suitable data types may exceed the timespan of EPOS ON, but, as a minimum requirement, we aim to offer at least borehole data and seismological monitoring data obtained at the Delft Campus Geothermal Project and the BedrettoLab in the GIM and Seismology TCS, respectively; in addition to these being offered by MSL as site-specific data.

Service provider: Utrecht University.

Data providers: among others, 4TU.ResearchData, GFZ data services, BGS NGDC, Fraunhofer institute; ETH Research Collection data repository.

4.4 Subtask 2.1.4: Enhance magnetotelluric data and models (LTU)

Subtask description: TCS Geomagnetic Observations (TCS GEOM) is responsible for the provision of Earth's natural electromagnetic field data originating from the Earth's interior, atmosphere, and space. Luleå University of Technology (LTU) is the TCS GEOM coordinator and the central hub for the EMTDAMO service. The latter provides the end-users with the opportunity to discover magnetotelluric data around Europe (electromagnetic data in the future).

4.4.1 List of services for this subtask to be integrated

In order to provide better interoperability with the EPOS Platform, and easy access and download of data shared by the EMTDAMO service, we develop a new platform for MT data hosting. The new platform will provide better searchability and easier integration of new data coming from data providers as well as support federated access to distributed MT data across Europe.

List of services:

- **EMTDAMO service of MT data and models**

Description: Enhanced and updated service will be released and operational under the duration of the EPOS ON project. New and historical MT data will be added to the service by extending the data service providers network. Additional efforts will be made to create and approve *IAGA Div VI*⁶ standard for magnetotelluric data and models exchange. The standard will be based on EPOS development and will include recent advances in the field to make it an international IAGA standard.

Service Provider: Luleå University of Technology.

Data Providers: Institutions across Europe collecting and hosting MT data.

⁶ <https://iaga-aiga.org/about/div6/>

4.5 Subtask 2.1.5: Muography density imaging (UOULU, AGH/AGH-UST)

Subtask description: Muography is a multidisciplinary research field that leverages the properties of cosmic-ray muons to investigate natural objects, infrastructure, and various environmental phenomena. Traditionally known as muon imaging, this technique has been widely used to probe the internal density distribution of large-scale structures, including geological formations such as volcanoes, caves, glaciers, and subsurface structures. As high-energy muons penetrate matter, their attenuation provides valuable insights into density variations, offering a non-invasive imaging method that complements conventional geophysical techniques.

Recent advancements have expanded the scope of muography beyond imaging applications. In addition to density imaging, muographic techniques now encompass positioning, navigation, time metrology, and cryptographic applications (Tanaka et al., 2023). For example, muometric positioning and navigation (muPS) offers solutions in GPS-denied environments, while cosmic time synchronization (CTS) and cosmic time calibration (CTC) enable high-precision timekeeping. Furthermore, muometric cryptography, such as cosmic coding and transfer (COSMOCAT), provides secure authentication protocols for data communication. However, within the EPOS ON project, the primary focus remains on muon imaging, particularly the integration of density imaging datasets into the EPOS infrastructure to enhance geophysical and environmental research.

- NOTE: To avoid misunderstandings, we will use the more specific term muon imaging rather than muography where necessary, ensuring clarity in discussions about the scope and objectives of the project.
- NOTE: When we use the term muography, we refer to a broader scope that includes not only muon imaging but also potential future services that could be integrated into EPOS. These additional services—such as muometric positioning (muPS), cosmic time synchronization, and other emerging applications—may become relevant once the foundational aspects of muon imaging data integration have been addressed. This stepwise approach ensures that muography-related research fields are incorporated systematically, allowing the muography research community, particularly the International Virtual Muography Institute (VMI), to be fully integrated into EPOS before expanding the available services.

Beyond solid Earth applications, muon imaging is also being explored for imaging atmospheric and oceanic phenomena (Tanaka et al., 2021, 2022a, 2022b). For example, recent studies have demonstrated its potential in imaging the density profiles of tropical cyclones, providing new insights into storm dynamics (Tanaka et al., 2022b). Similarly, in glaciology, muographic methods are being applied to analyze ice structure and melting processes, contributing to climate and environmental studies.

As an evolving and expanding field, muography holds significant promise for geosciences, environmental monitoring, climate studies, and even advanced technological applications. In

collaboration with Work Package WP5 of the EPOS ON project, the muography community is working towards integrating publicly available muon imaging datasets into the European Plate Observing System (EPOS). This initiative aims to establish standardized data formats for muographic imaging measurements, ensuring interoperability and accessibility across research institutions and facilitating broader scientific collaboration.

4.5.1 List of services for this subtask to be integrated

Muon imaging as a method overlaps with multiple Thematic Core Services (TCS) within the EPOS platform. Within the EPOS ON timeframe, the subtask will focus on investigating the most suitable integration strategy for muon imaging datasets. This will include design discussions and architectural considerations to determine whether muon imaging data should be integrated into an existing TCS (e.g., anthropogenic hazards), multiple TCSs, or if a dedicated Muography TCS prototype should be developed. A decision on the integration approach will be made during the EPOS ON project period based on these discussions and community feedback. This approach aims to maximize interdisciplinarity and enhance the interoperability of muon imaging data with existing datasets from other methodologies within the EPOS platform. By doing so, muon imaging can contribute to a broader range of geoscientific applications and foster more comprehensive data analysis across disciplines.

While the primary focus in EPOS ON is muon imaging, the longer-term vision includes a broader scope under muography, which encompasses additional services such as muometric positioning, cosmic time synchronization, and other emerging applications. These future services could be integrated into EPOS once the foundational aspects of muon imaging data standardization and interoperability have been established, and the muography research community—particularly the International Virtual Muography Institute (VMI)—has been fully integrated into the EPOS framework.

However, these additional developments are likely beyond the scope of the current EPOS ON project due to limited resources and the rapid evolution of muography as a research field. While muon imaging itself is still relatively new in geophysical applications, the other methods under the broader muography umbrella—such as the emerging muometric positioning and cosmic time synchronization—are even newer and still in an early stage of technological validation. Given the fundamental differences in data types, applications, and integration requirements, these advancements require separate considerations beyond the current EPOS ON project. While their future inclusion in EPOS remains an open possibility, the immediate focus is on integrating muon imaging data in a way that sets the foundation for potential expansions into these newer technologies once the necessary technical and scientific frameworks are in place. However, within this project, the scope is to concentrate on muon imaging and both service and data providers within the field.

List of services:

- **Muon Imaging Data Integration**

Description: Muon imaging data consists of geotagged density measurements, meaning each measurement is assigned precise geographical coordinates (latitude, longitude, and sometimes elevation). These geotagged data points allow for accurate spatial referencing and integration with Geographic Information Systems (GIS). Muon imaging data can be represented as 2D or 3D images, with a temporal (4D) component to track density changes over time. This dataset is essential for visualizing geological, atmospheric, and oceanic structures and their dynamic behaviors.

Service Providers: Institutions, research groups, and companies hosting muon imaging data and managing its accessibility. The work will concentrate on connecting with the members of the International Virtual Muography Institute ([VMI](#)).

Data Providers: Institutions, research groups, and companies conducting muon imaging surveys and generating datasets, including members of the [VMI](#). Given the growing global interest in muon imaging integration within broader geoscience infrastructures, such as the EPOS, collaboration between EPOS and VMI is being explored. Additionally, existing long-term muon imaging datasets, such as those from the JP-HU Sakurajima Muography Observatory, provide an opportunity for incorporating large-scale muon imaging data into EPOS services. The “JP-HU” in the “JP-HU Sakurajima Muography Observatory” refers to the collaborative nature of the observatory management between Japan and Hungary.

Future efforts will focus on standardizing muon imaging survey data and metadata to ensure interoperability and comparability across different datasets. While the EPOS ON project is dedicated to integrating muon imaging, the broader scope of muography, which includes applications such as muometric positioning and cosmic time synchronization, may be considered for future EPOS expansions once muon imaging data integration has been successfully established and the muography research community, particularly VMI, has been fully integrated into EPOS.

Roadmap:

The integration of muon imaging into EPOS has just begun through work package WP5 of the EPOS ON project, with efforts to engage the muon imaging community and relevant Thematic Core Services (TCS). The first official meeting with muon imaging researchers (also known as “muographers”) is scheduled for **2025-Q1**, marking the initial step toward collaboration and data integration.

- **2025-Q4:** Estimated timeline for the first version of the standardized muon imaging data structure, ensuring that geotagged density data can be properly formatted and integrated into EPOS (development stage).

- **2026-Q2:** Expected period for testing and integration of muon imaging data into the EPOS platform.
- **2027-Q1:** Pilot muon imaging datasets are expected to be fully integrated into EPOS, possibly within one or more TCSs. This milestone will serve as a proof of concept (PoC) for the interoperability of muon imaging data within EPOS and will lay the foundation for future large-scale data sharing and standardization efforts.

By ensuring geotagging and standardization, the integration of muon imaging data will enable seamless interdisciplinary collaboration, allowing researchers to correlate muon imaging findings with other geophysical datasets and expand the range of scientific insights derived from EPOS.

4.6 Subtask 2.1.6: World Stress Map (GFZ)

Subtask description: The World Stress Map (WSM) database will be expanded with stress magnitude and pore pressure data. The open-access database, which currently only provides data on the orientation of the stress tensor and stress regime, serves a wide range of Earth science disciplines such as geodynamics, hazard assessment, reservoir exploration, and geotechnical engineering.

4.6.1 List of services for this subtask to be integrated

In Fig. 1, we show an overview of the general workflow of the further development of the **WSM database project**. The upper blue boxes show the data acquisition level which will be expanded by the stress magnitude and pore pressure data. The green and grey boxes are the technical level with the new repository for stress information that will integrate the future separated data types and references for these data records. The orange boxes denote the user interface and public access level to the data. Below the three key new services that we intend to develop and to integrate into the WSM are described in more detail.

Fig. 3. General concept of the envisioned developments of the World Stress Map (WSM) project as a unique global repository for contemporary crustal stress information. Currently, the WSM contains only data for the orientation of the maximum horizontal stress S_{Hmax} . After the WSM release 2025 in April we will use the new MaRS database infrastructure to facilitate the WSM expansion with pore pressure and stress magnitude data.

List of services:

- **Development of the new WSM database infrastructure MaRS**

Description: **MaRS** is an acronym for **M**anagement and **R**epository of **S**tress. The development of MaRS is an essential step for the future to facilitate the integration of new data into the WSM database. MaRS has a web-based user interface where the information of data from different sources are typed in. The quality assignment and other calculations are then performed automatically with internal Python routines. Furthermore, MaRS also integrates the database of the literature (bibliography) that is linked to the individual data records. Currently, we store more than 2.000 pdf files of paper and reports. MaRS will be the backbone of the WSM project and allow the integration of all data types.

Service Provider: GFZ Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences.

Data Providers: WSM Team⁷.

- **New WSM database 2025 release**

Description: Using MaRS we will release at the EGU General Assembly 2025 in Vienna a new WSM database of the orientation of the maximum horizontal stress S_{Hmax} including > 3,000 newly analyzed borehole data. This new release will have more than double the number of data records (>100,000) compared to the last release of the WSM in 2016 (with approximately 42,000 data records, Heidbach et al, 2018). The new WSM database release comes along with an update of the WSM quality ranking scheme and a number of changes. The most important ones are: a) the introduction of a new quality class for data where the information is incomplete (Xmi quality) or from stress indicators that are not established (Xne), b) skipping the old limit of compiling only data up to 40 km depth and use now the global crustal model of Szwillus et al. (2019), c) we integrate the global focal mechanisms catalog of the ISC, and d) we rearrange the data fields to meet with developments in the past decade.

Service Provider: GFZ Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences.

Data Providers: International collaborators⁸, published data in papers and reports and own analysis of raw data such as borehole logs or compilations of earthquake focal mechanisms.

- **Expansion of the WSM database with stress magnitude and pore pressure data**

Description: So far, the WSM compiles and provides only data records on the S_{Hmax} orientation. In the next but one WSM database release, we envision to provide also a compilation of stress magnitude data quality-ranked using the quality ranking scheme of Morawietz et al. (2021). And the year after we will add the next data type of quality-ranked pore pressure data. The quality-ranking scheme is currently under development with an international team of experts from academia and industry and will be presented at the end of 2025 in a scientific paper to a larger audience. As the WSM database increases in complexity, the MaRS infrastructure will be further developed to handle the data and to guarantee a safe long-term repository. The same holds on for the web-based user interface **CASMO**⁹ (Create A Stress Map Online).

⁷ <https://www.world-stress-map.org/team>

⁸ https://www.world-stress-map.org/fileadmin/wsm/pdfs/WSM_Contributor.pdf

⁹ <https://www.world-stress-map.org/casmo>

Service Provider: GFZ Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences.

Data Providers: International collaborator, published data in papers and reports, and own analysis of raw data.

4.7 Subtask 2.1.7: Coordinated inventory of mobile instrument pools (GFZ)

Subtask description: A prototype inventory of mobile instrument pools in Europe for TCS Seismology will be created and made available to increase knowledge of these facilities, enable coordinated field experiments, and increase usage of the instruments. GFZ will coordinate this service within the framework of the Mobile Pools group of ORFEUS¹⁰. An automated mechanism will be proposed to exchange information about mobile equipment and make it discoverable via a web interface and web service.

4.7.1 List of for this subtask to be integrated

The European Mobile Seismic Instrument Pools (EUSIP), coordinated within ORFEUS, are working on the formal framework for collaboration and information exchange regarding the specifics of the facilities and the instrument availability at each pool. This would be particularly important for large-scale seismic experiments (LARGE-N¹¹), which often require access to distributed resources.

A service able to provide that information consistently acquired from the various providers does not yet exist. Thus we plan to actually build this prototype service within this task.

List of services:

- **Coordinated inventory of mobile instrument pools**

Description: The service will provide information about the instruments generally available in the pools and their terms of use (if development time permits, the adoption of existing guidelines will be considered). The information is collected in a central database, merged, and eventually made available via a micro API, according to the general definition of a data schema. Each pool provides updated information as soon as an update is necessary (instruments added or decommissioned, new bookings or existing ones canceled, policy updates, etc.). The subtask will also explore the feasibility of exposing the actual availability of instruments in the future (depending on the bookings already made) which should also be recorded and made accessible. Finally, a lightweight front-end for ORFEUS (similar to the EIDA portal) is developed using this API, allowing users to browse through pools (and time) and search for available instruments. The API will also be able to be used by other services (i.e., EPOS portal or at each pool).

¹⁰ <https://orfeus-eu.org/>

¹¹ array of many instruments in the area

Service Provider: GFZ/ORFEUS service would run at least at one of the two servers (domains) and would be an ORFEUS service developed and provided by GFZ.

Data Providers: EU pools - part of the EU Mobile Seismic Instrument Pool¹² listed here. As soon as new Instrument providers join this group they provide new data. Possible current data providers are:

- Geophysical Instrument Pool Potsdam - GIPP (Germany)
- Mobile Seismic Pool - SisMob (France)
- Sismologie Mobile Marine - SMM (France)
- LabSis (Spain)
- SEIS-UK (UK)

4.8 Subtask 2.1.8: Harmonized data and associated data services for V_{s30} , slope, and geology (BRGM)

Subtask description: The purpose of task 2.1.8 is to allow access to data sets suitable for seismological purposes, in particular those useful to characterize site properties or to assess the susceptibility to seismic site effects. Those data are essential to assess large-scale seismic hazard and risk models such as the ESHM20 and ESRM20 models available on the EFEHR¹³ portal (European Facilities for Earthquake Hazard and Risk). Among the different harmonized data sets that will be provided through EPOS, some were used in order to model site response at a regional scale for the 2020 European Seismic Risk Model (ESRM20) during the European SERA¹⁴ project (e.g., Weatherill et al., 2023). Such different European data sets consist of either maps (e.g., geological maps) or data from specific points (e.g., seismic wave velocity measures) and provide information useful for identifying any potential ground amplification susceptibilities in response to seismic ground motion. These data sets are likely to evolve in order to remain consistent with other initiatives (e.g., EGDI products and developments).

However, it is important to underline the fact that site effects are local phenomena, whereas models of site characterization based on data available on a continental scale are no substitute for ad hoc studies based especially on dense local measurement surveys.

4.8.1 List of services for this subtask to be integrated

Some harmonized Europe-wide datasets have been previously built in order to develop and evaluate some models of site characterization that could be considered for seismic hazard and risk assessment at a large scale. Such work was carried out as part of past European SHARE

¹² <http://www.orfeus-eu.org/data/mobile/>

¹³ <http://www.efehr.org/>

¹⁴ <http://www.sera-eu.org/>

(<http://www.share-eu.org>) and SERA projects (<http://www.sera-eu.org>). Data sets to be integrated in EPOS:

- Harmonized Europe-wide geology map simplified in order to be devoted to site effects purposes.
- DEM and DEM-derived elements (slopes)
- Compilation of measured V_{s30} Data Across Europe
- Test for the integration of a local-scale dataset for site effect characterization (proof of concept)

List of services:

- **Harmonized Europe-wide dataset of geology map using OneGeology and Promine**

Description: A geological map was simplified and harmonized from the 1:1,500,000 scale map from the ProMine European project, completed for recent formations (NE Europe) with information from the OneGeology 1:1,000,000 scale map. See Weatherall et al. (2023) for a better description and Deliverable D26.4 from the SERA project. Thanks to this a litho-stratigraphic map over Europe is available, with simplified lithological codes and stratigraphic coding focused on quaternary and tertiary formations (a priori most prone to site effect), and lithological and stratigraphic codes are associated with shapefiles. This work was performed in 2018, and it should be relevant to check with the EGDI¹⁵ group whether progress has been made in terms of harmonization or completeness in European geological maps.

Service Provider: EUCENTRE (for EFEHR)¹⁶; Stratigraphic map. A lithological map is still not provided online but should be available in 2026 (probably on EasyData, the French “Earth System Data repository” [EaSy Data](#)).

Data Providers: Compilation, simplification, and harmonization performed by BRGM from ProMine and OneGeology maps provided by European projects and groups (e.g., EGDI¹⁷).

- **DEM and DEM-derived elements (slopes)**

Description: Digital Elevation Models (at the European scale) exist at different resolutions and are regularly updated. In order to be coherent with the classical Wald and Allen (2007) method (and with the continental scale) that proposes a correlation between the topographical slopes and V_{s30} , the 30-arc second resolution map for slope is shared from Gebco_2014 DEM. Gebco_2014 includes bathymetric compilations and land topography

¹⁵ <https://www.europe-geology.eu/>

¹⁶ <https://maps.eu-risk.eucentre.it/map/european-site-response-model-datasets/#4/53.96/4.57>

¹⁷ <https://www.europe-geology.eu/>

based on SRTM30 (Becker et al., 2009, Farr et al., 2007). Although newer, more detailed elevation data exists (like Gebco_2023), this map uses the same resolution as the 2007 Wald and Allen method for consistency. We calculated V_{s30} values from a slope, following Wald and Allen (2007), and divided Europe into "stable" and "active" zones based on Delavaud et al. (2012). Users will be notified that this is a rough estimate and should rely on local data or studies when available.

Service Provider: EUCENTRE (EFEHR)¹⁸; slope map and estimated V_{s30} from slope map.

Data Providers: (institutions providing data to the service) GEBCO¹⁹ for the DEM, slope from it by BRGM.

- **Compilation of measured V_{s30} data across Europe**

Description: During the European SERA project, a data set of measured V_{s30} (S wave velocity at 30m depth) has been compiled in order to confront these observations to models. Available public data on-site characterization were collected at the European scale from the European Engineering Strong Motion (ESM) database (Luzi et al., 2016, for Greece, Italy, and Turkey) added by national compilations (Portugal, France, Switzerland, Netherlands,...) available within scientific publications. This dataset is very important for seismic hazard assessment and should evolve with new measurements and more complete observations than only the V_{s30} value for each site. The shared data set was built in 2019 during the SERA project.

Service Provider: EUCENTRE (EFEHR)²⁰; a compilation of measured V_{s30}

Data Providers: ESM DB²¹ and for national or regional compilations: Lemoine et al. (2012), Roullé et al. (2010), Vilanova et al. (2018), Noorlandt et al., (2018), Stewart et al., (2014), Yilmaz et al., (2014).

- **Test for the integration of a local-scale dataset for site effect characterization (proof of concept)**

Description: Site effects are local effects, whereas simplified models based on large-scale data sets can lead to huge approximations. In order to illustrate the discrepancy between large-scale models or datasets with local studies or observations, and with the aim to highlight spatial heterogeneities problems, some local scale datasets will be shared: (1) the

¹⁸ <https://maps.eu-risk.eucentre.it/map/european-site-response-model-datasets/#4/53.96/4.57>

¹⁹ https://www.gebco.net/data_and_products/gridded_bathymetry_data/

²⁰ <https://maps.eu-risk.eucentre.it/map/european-site-response-model-datasets/#4/53.96/4.57>

²¹ <https://esm-db.eu/#/home>

local scale seismic microzonation of the Pyrenean cities of Lourdes and Bagnères-de-Luchon and (2) the regional scale zonation of the Pyrenean Range used for rapid-response tools²².

Service Provider: These data sets are still not provided online but should be available in 2026 (probably on EasyData, the French “earth system data repository” [EaSy Data](#)).

Data Providers: BRGM.

4.9 Subtask 2.1.9: Computation of Rapid solutions in GNSS (UGA, UBI)

Subtask description: This subtask focuses on the automated computation and dissemination of GNSS station position time series using rapid orbit solutions. The responsibility for the development of the computational workflow lies with UGA, ensuring that rapid solutions are available within 2 days of data acquisition. UBI will manage the dissemination of these solutions through the GNSS-EPOS products portal²³, making them accessible for scientific and operational applications.

The processing strategy will involve the generation of daily coordinate solutions using rapid GNSS orbit products. These solutions will be computed in a fully automated manner, ensuring internal consistency with the geodetic reference frame adopted within EPOS. The primary goal is to provide users with timely position time series that capture transient geophysical signals, including tectonic motions, post-seismic relaxation, and volcanic or hydrological deformation.

To ensure accessibility and ease of integration with other EPOS services, the position time series will be made available in different formats like JSON, a widely used standard for geodetic data exchange. Each dataset will include coordinate time series in the north, east, and vertical components, along with estimated uncertainties. A structured metadata system will also be implemented to provide clear information on processing parameters, reference frames, and potential limitations.

The significance of this service is illustrated in Figure 2, which presents the rapid GNSS-derived position time series for a recent episode of seismic unrest in Santorini, Greece. The figure demonstrates how horizontal (latitude and longitude) and vertical displacements can be detected, with trends indicating ongoing ground deformation. Such rapid solutions are critical for real-time monitoring of geophysical hazards and for integrating GNSS observations into early-warning and risk assessment frameworks.

²² products from SISPYR <http://www.sispyr.eu/> and POCRISC <https://pocrisc.eu> european projects

²³ <https://gnssproducts.epos.ubi.pt/>

Fig. 2. Time-series for SANTO0GRC (Santorini, Greece) station showing the non-linear movement of this station due to a dyke intrusion. It is a very clear the recent deformation signal, particularly in the North (Latitude) component.

4.9.1 List of services for this subtask to be integrated

- **Service 1: Rapid Position Time-Series Computation**

Description: This service provides the automated computation of daily GNSS station positions using rapid orbit solutions, ensuring the availability of high-quality position time series within 2 days of data acquisition. The processing workflow is designed to maintain consistency with the geodetic reference frames adopted within EPOS while allowing for rapid response to geophysical events. The solutions will be generated in a fully automated manner, with internal quality control procedures to ensure reliability.

Service Provider: University of Grenoble Alpes (UGA).

Data Providers: EPOS GNSS network operators.

- **Service 2: Dissemination of Rapid Position Time-Series**

Description: This service ensures the structured dissemination of the computed GNSS position time series through the GNSS-EPOS products portal. The time series will be provided in JSON format, including coordinates in the north, east, and vertical components, associated uncertainties, and metadata detailing processing parameters and reference frames. The data will be accessible through a dedicated interface, enabling integration with visualization and analysis tools within the EPOS ecosystem.

Service Provider: University of Beira Interior (UBI)

Data Providers: University of Grenoble Alpes (UGA)

4.10 Subtask 2.1.10: Airborne survey data (GEOSPHERE)

Subtask description: Airborne magnetic data will be standardized and made accessible to support research in fault detection, investigation of tectonic structures, intrusions, and monitoring of volcanic areas.

4.10.1 List of services for this subtask to be integrated

A service providing metadata information on conducted **airborne magnetic surveys** and, if freely available, **gridded data of the magnetic anomaly field** as well as the **position of flight lines** and the possibility of downloading the data. OGC²⁴-compliant services provided for EPOS will come from the service provider EGD. Data shown on EGD will come from GeoSphere OGC-compliant services.

The first three assets (made bold above) will be made available over the WMS service of GeoSphereMaps interfaced over EGD with EPOS, the latter will most probably be linked over the certified research data repository Tethys²⁵.

For data harmonization, we will use the platform of the newly founded Geophysical expert group of EuroGeoSurveys to try to decide on European-wide standards: most likely, members of the subtask will join the new initiative on a global standard for geophysical data, i.e., the OGC led by the USGS²⁶, together with Geoscience Australia²⁷ (GA) and the Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation²⁸ (CSIRO) and others.

²⁴ <https://www.ogc.org/>

²⁵ <https://www.tethys.at/>

²⁶ <https://www.usgs.gov/>

²⁷ <https://www.ga.gov.au/>

²⁸ <https://www.csiro.au/>

List of services:

- **Airborne magnetic surveys of Europe**

Description: Metadata and, if free access is available, data from airborne magnetic surveys acquired within Europe.

Service Provider: GeoSphere Austria (Tethys data repository and GeoSphereMaps²⁹, interface to EPOS over EGDI).

Data Providers: GeoSphere Austria, Geophysical expert group of EuroGeoSurvey (EGS).

²⁹ <https://maps.geosphere.at>

4.11 Service integration timeline

Services from all subtasks are summarized in Table 2, including the expected integration timeline. The actual integration progress will be followed through the **Implementation Level Matrix (ILM)** provided as a shared online spreadsheet. The spreadsheet can be updated by partners anytime and will be used for annual project reporting (technical reports).

Table 2 - Service integration timeline (2025-Q1 - 2027-Q2)

Integration timeline				
Service title (subtask number)	Development stage until	Testing integration EPOS until	and into	Integrated into EPOS
<u>Multidisciplinary data: Micro-climatic data from Slovenian Karst (2.1.1)</u>	2026-Q2	2026-Q4		2027-Q2
<u>Multidisciplinary data: Seismic data from Slovenian Karst (2.1.1)</u>	2026-Q1	2026-Q3		2027-Q1
<u>Real-time and Discrete Geochemical Data Repository (2.1.2)</u>	2026-Q3	2027-Q1		2027-Q2
<u>Machine learning-driven Data Validation and Predictive Maintenance System (2.1.2)</u>	2026-Q3	2027-Q1		2027-Q2
<u>Automatic Alert System for Geochemical Anomalies (2.1.2)</u>	2026-Q3	2027-Q1		2027-Q2
<u>A new MSL service for site-specific GETB data (2.1.3)</u>	2026-Q1	2026-Q3		2026-Q4
<u>Services for multi-domain GETB data dissemination (2.1.3)</u>	2026-Q4	2027-Q1		2027-Q2
<u>Enhance magnetotelluric data and models (2.1.4)</u>	2025-Q4	2026-Q2		2026-Q4
<u>Muography data (2.1.5)</u>	2025-Q4	2026-Q2		2027-Q1
<u>Development of the new WSM database infrastructure MaRS (2.1.6)</u>	2025-Q2	2025-Q4		2026-Q1
<u>New WSM database 2025 release (2.1.6)</u>	2025-Q2	2025-Q4		2026-Q2
<u>Expansion of the WSM database with stress magnitude and pore pressure data (2.1.6)</u>	2026-Q4	2027-Q1		2027-Q2
<u>Coordinated inventory of mobile instrument pools (2.1.7)</u>	2025-Q4	2026-Q1		2026-Q2
<u>Simplified and harmonized litho-stratigraphic maps (2.1.8)</u>	2026-Q4	2027-Q1		2027-Q2

Integration timeline				
Service title (subtask number)	Development stage until	Testing integration EPOS until	and into	Integrated into EPOS
DEM and DEM-derived elements - slopes (2.1.8)	2026-Q2	2026-Q4		2027-Q2
Compilation of measured V_{s30} data across Europe (2.1.8)	2026-Q2	2026-Q4		2027-Q2
Test for the integration of a local-scale dataset for site effect characterisation (proof of concept, additional; 2.1.8)	2026-Q4	2027-Q1		2027-Q2
Rapid Position Time-Series Computation (2.1.9)	2026-Q4	2027-Q1		2027-Q2
Dissemination of Rapid Position Time-Series (2.1.9)	2026-Q4	2027-Q1		2027-Q2
Airborne magnetic survey data (2.1.10)	2026-Q2	2026-Q4		2027-Q2

5 References

- Becker, J. J., D. T. Sandwell, W. H. F. Smith, J. Braud, B. Binder, J. L. Depner, ... & P. Weatherall, (2009). Global bathymetry and elevation data at 30 arc seconds resolution: SRTM30_PLUS. *Marine Geodesy*, 32(4), 355-371.
- Delavaud, E., F. Cotton, S. Akkar, F. Scherbaum, L. Danciu, C. Beauval, ... & N. Theodoulidis, (2012). Toward a ground-motion logic tree for probabilistic seismic hazard assessment in Europe. *Journal of Seismology*, 16, 451-473.
- Farr, T. G., P. A. Rosen, E. Caro, R. Crippen, R. Duren, S. Hensley, ... & D. Alsdorf, (2007). The shuttle radar topography mission. *Reviews of Geophysics*, 45(2).
- [Gemini AI](#), a large language model from Google. Accessed 2025-02-03. Prompt “Describe the procedure for integrating new service into EPOS infrastructure”.
- Heidbach, O., Rajabi, M., Cui, X., Fuchs, K., Müller, B., Reinecker, J., Reiter, K., Tingay, M., Wenzel, F., Xie, F., Ziegler, M. O., Zoback, M.-L., and Zoback, M. D.: The World Stress Map database release 2016: Crustal stress pattern across scales, *Tectonophysics*, 744, 484-498, 10.1016/j.tecto.2018.07.007, 2018.
- Lemoine A., J. Douglas, and F. Cotton. (2012), Testing the applicability of correlations between topographic slope and VS 30 for Europe, *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America* 102.6, 2585-2599.
- Luzi L., et al. (2016), The engineering strong-motion database: A platform to access Pan-European accelerometric data, *Seismological Research Letters*, 87.4, 987-997.
- Morawietz, S., O. Heidbach, K. Reiter, M. O. Ziegler, M. Rajabi, G. Zimmerman, B. Müller, and M. Tingay (2020), An open-access stress magnitude database for Germany and adjacent regions, *Geothermal Energy*, doi:10.1186/s40517-020-00178-5.
- Noorlandt R., et al. (2018), Characterisation of ground motion recording stations in the Groningen gas field, *Journal of seismology*, 22, 605-623.
- Roullé A., S. Auclair, T. Dewez, A. Hohmann, A. Lemoine and J. Rey (2010), Cartographie automatique des classes de sol a l'échelle régionale à partir d'un modèle numérique de terrain ou de surface, Rapport final, <http://infoterre.brgm.fr/rapports/RP-58853-FR.pdf>
- Stewart, J. P., et al. (2014), Compilation of a local VS profile database and its application for inference of VS 30 from geologic-and terrain-based proxies, *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 104.6, 2827-2841.

Szwillus, W., J. C. Afonso, J. Ebbing, and W. D. Mooney (2019), Global Crustal Thickness and Velocity Structure From Geostatistical Analysis of Seismic Data, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth*, 124(2), 1626-1652, doi:10.1029/2018jb016593.

Tanaka, H.K.M., et al. (2021), First results of undersea muography with the Tokyo-Bay Seafloor Hyper-Kilometric Submarine Deep Detector, *Scientific Reports*, 11, 19485, doi:10.1038/s41598-021-98559-8.

Tanaka, H.K.M., et al. (2022a), Periodic Sea-Level Oscillation in Tokyo Bay Detected with the Tokyo-Bay Seafloor Hyper-Kilometric Submarine Deep Detector (TS-HKMSDD), *Scientific Reports*, 12, 6097. doi:10.1038/s41598-022-10078-2.

Tanaka, H.K.M., et al. (2022b), Atmospheric muography for imaging and monitoring tropic cyclones, *Scientific Reports*, 12, 16710, doi:10.1038/s41598-022-20039-4.

Vilanova, S. P., et al. (2018), Developing a geologically based V_{s30} site-condition model for Portugal: Methodology and assessment of the performance of proxies, *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 108.1, 322-337.

Wald, David J., and T. I. Allen. (2007), Topographic slope as a proxy for seismic site conditions and amplification, *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 97.5, 1379-1395.

Weatherill, G., et al. (2023), Modelling site response at regional scale for the 2020 European Seismic Risk Model (ESRM20), *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering*, 21.2., 665-714.

Yilmaz, M. T, A. Ansari, and E. Harmandar. (2014), Simple geological categories as proxies to V_{s30} in Turkey and Iran, in *The Proceedings of the second European conference on earthquake engineering and seismology, Istanbul August*, pp. 25-29.